

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_a_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:23:16 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	15.89	µm	
Size:	65531	digits	
Spacing:	0.2425	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_a_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:23:16 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	7.445	μm	
Min:	-5.51	μm	
Max:	1.935	μm	
Size:	306978	digits	
Spacing:	0.02425	nm	
NM-points ratio:	2.447 % (220197 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 4:23:16 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	7.445	μm	
Size:	306978	digits	
Spacing:	0.02425	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.6036	μm	
Ssk	-2.255		
Sku	20.73		
Sp	1.933	μm	
Sv	5.512	μm	
Sz	7.445	μm	
Sa	0.3858	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	4.761	%	
Smc	0.6318	μm	
Sxp	1.019	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	19.06	μm	
Str	0.5135		
Std	35.99	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1478		
Sdr	1.025	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.03589	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	0.6677	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.03589	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.3554	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.5856	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.08216	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

- ISO 25178 8.
- Furrow 9.
- Texture direction 10.
- Texture isotropy 11.
- SSFA 12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	3.582	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.3759	µm
Mean density of furrows	4260	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	45.01	°
Second direction	135.0	°
Third direction	90.02	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	81.54	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

